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Convergence and divergence in the eastern Circum-Baltic Area
(A triangulation approach)
Vol. I: Northern Part

SUPPLEMENT

Loose guidelines for portraits of varieties (Ch. 2)

GENERAL:

- Critical survey and review of the extant literature (including own work and unpublished material); assess how far issues in phonology, morphology, syntax and the lexicon have been investigated so far (including diachrony), and also to what extent contact with other varieties has been taken into consideration.
- As far as possible, account for the features mentioned in the Appendix to the project application, apart from the structural properties listed below. The structural properties under #2 below are meant as a checklist to guide you through grammatical properties. Not all issues may be equally relevant for “your” variety (either because the structure does not have such phenomena or because the variety is yet too poorly described), but in such cases it is important to state that explicitly (i.e. by saying that such and such phenomena are not attested).
- The list below is NOT exhaustive; thus, you may add further properties you consider important for the general profile of “your” variety (on its immediate or larger areal and/or genealogical background).
- Account for diachronic development and sociolinguistic situation (including contact with other languages or dialects) as far as possible.
- IF POSSIBLE (e.g. if the relevant data are available), an inclusion of usage-based (token-oriented) accounts would be most desirable, as well as an account of admissible lexical input of constructions (grams). Many grammatical constructions “grow” to a different extent (e.g., resultatives are by definition restricted to inherently telic verbal roots, while tense is basically unrestricted), and if the admissible lexical input of a construction increases the initial functions of that construction deteriorate (e.g., resultatives become perfects, anticausatives become passives or impersonals).
- We suggest that the description starts with the more general profile of the features common to the whole group of varieties you describe and then proceeds with those features that distinguish individual varieties; thus, we are aiming at a unified description that would make similarities and differences between varieties as clear and explicit as possible.

NOTE:

- The term “variety” is meant to cover any sort of lect: language, dialect, vernacular, dolect...
- Critical remarks and questions are most welcome.

The proposed structure:

1. Basic information about location, genealogical affiliation, speakers (where, how many speakers), sociolinguistic situation, including relations with dominant language(s)/variety(ies)

and issues of bi-/multilingualism (e.g. percentage of bilingual speakers with possible generation/gender/social stratification), possible language shift, attrition etc. — i.e. a general characteristic of the language contact situation.

2. Structural properties (first of all on a synchronic level, but with an account of diachrony, where possible, as well)

- Please, remark if there are any discernible MAT- or PAT-borrowings (cf. Sakel 2007) for any of the features mentioned below.

2.1. Phonetics, phonological contrasts (if possible also syllable structure) and automatic phonological processes.

2.2. Morphophonological alternations (i.e. those induced not just by phonotactic constraints but by considerations of morphological structure, e.g. *peku* ~ *pečēt* alternation in Russian)

2.3. Syntactic classes (Parts-of-Speech), with remarks on how clear-cut these classes are and where classifying problems arise in the first place (e.g. mismatches between morphological and syntactic criteria).

2.4. Morphological categories/features (e.g. tense) and subcategories/values (e.g. past) (on the background of (i) genealogically closest and (ii) areally closest varieties). Interactions between them (mutual conditioning, syncretism, portmanteau-morphemes).

2.5. Is allomorphy complex (opaque) or rather transparent (e.g. such phenomena as fusion, stem alternations etc.)? Does it happen to be difficult to determine conditioned allomorphy against free variation? Are there inflectional classes?

2.6. Relation between inflectional and derivational morphology:

- a) How clear-cut is this distinction in “your” variety? Where do you find cases difficult to determine? (Cf. e.g. the controversy about the status of participles or Slavic aspect.)
- b) What are the most important functions of derivational processes (for different parts of speech)? Are there morphological processes which change resp. preserve the syntactic class (part-of-speech) of the base?
- c) To what degree is derivational resp. inflectional morphology elaborated in nominal resp. verbal domains in paradigmatic (e.g. number of cases / tenses / verbal perfectivizing prefixes) and syntagmatic (e.g. maximal number of categories / morphemes per word) terms?
- d) Which types of exponents (suffixes, prefixes, non-concatenative exponents such as ablaut, stem alternations etc.) are more characteristic of inflectional resp. derivational morphology of nominals resp. verbs?

2.7. Clitics: do clitics form a morpheme class with distinct morphosyntactic behavior?

- What belongs to this class (pronouns, auxiliaries)?
- Are there clitic strings/clusters? If yes, what elements occur in them and in which order?
- What are the positional properties of clitics/clitic clusters (e.g. Wackernagel clitics)?

2.8. Which modifiers of verbal action (‘satellites’ in terms of Talmy 1985, see also Wälchli 2001) are used: preverbs, (ad)verbal particles, gerunds etc.? How far do they coalesce with the verbal stems they modify (on a free—clitic—agglutinated—fused cline)? What are the differences between distinct types of ‘satellites’ (cf. e.g. prefixes vs. adverbial particles in Latvian, see Wälchli 2001)?

2.9. Morphological cases and adpositions: range of functions, syncretisms, interaction with other nominal categories (see 2.4). Consider not only

- functions to mark (core or peripheral) arguments, but also
- clear adjunct/adverbial functions (e.g. the temporal accusative) or
- functions conditioned by special constructions (e.g., the genitive/dative of goal in Lithuanian, marking of the predicate nominal etc.).

Furthermore:

- What about genitive/partitive of negation?
- What about differential subject/object marking? What triggers it?

2.10. What is (if any) the basic order of major sentence constituents (subject, object, verb)?

- Do such parameters as syntactic weight (length in words), noun vs. pronoun, main vs. subordinate clause affect the position of subject and/or object with respect to the verb or to each other?
- Is it possible to manipulate word order for the purposes of information structure (topicalization/focalization)? Are there any dedicated positions for topic or focus?
- Is there movement of question words, if yes, what is their normal position? How are yes/no questions formed? Is there a question particle, what is its position?
- What are the orders inside the major constituents, e.g. noun-adjective, noun-genitive attribute (and also when there is both an adjective and a genitive attribute), noun-adposition? Are there variable orders? If yes, which factors determine them (e.g., the adnominal genitive in Lithuanian is normally preposed to its head, but it is postposed if it marks indefinite quantity: *arbat-os.GEN puodukas* ‘tea cup’ vs. *puodukas arbat-os.GEN* ‘a cup of tea’)

2.11. Agreement within NPs and on clause level, and lack of agreement. Syntactic relations marked by agreement (e.g. subject-predicate or modifier-noun) and factors conditioning lack of agreement.

2.12. (Non)finiteness:

- What are the morphological and/or syntactic properties of verb forms used as independent predicates as opposed to those used as subordinate predicates? Agreement with subject in person/number/gender? Expression of mood/tense? Any special morphology?
- Do all verbal forms used as independent predicates share these features (e.g. in East Slavic only present tense verbs inflect for person; in Latvian evidential and subjunctive forms do not show agreement)? What are the characteristic syntactic features of independent predicates as opposed to subordinate? E.g. presence of overt subject marked by the nominative case (in Lithuanian this is possible for participles used as evidential main predicates but not for participles in other uses; in Russian the infinitive can be used as an independent predicate, but normally requires a dative subject, cf. *mne ujtī?* 1SG.DAT go.out.INF ‘should I go?’).

2.13. Specifically on ‘participles’:

- Are there non-finite verbal forms used as attributes to nouns and behaving like adjectives? Do these forms have voice orientation (as e.g. in Slavic and Baltic)? Are there non-oriented participles (cf. Haspelmath 1994; Wiemer 2014: 1629-1631)?
- Do these forms have any other uses, e.g. as heads of complement or adverbial clauses, or as independent predicates? Do they show identical or different morphological /

syntactic properties in different uses?

- If some participial constructions may function as independent predications, what is their range of functions in narrative and isolated sentences?

2.14. Valency and argument structure:

- Valency-reducing means (e.g., reflexive markers), valency-increasing means (e.g., causatives, applicatives); constructions demoting the highest-ranking argument (usually Actor) and means to mark this demoted argument (e.g., oblique case, PP).
- Note that apart from the passive there may be Actor-demoting constructions with zero marking and resting just on a functional transposition (like, e.g., Slavic 3.PL-constructions with “zeroed” subject as equivalents of German *man*-constructions: Russ. *V dver’ postučali* ‘Somebody knocked at the door’ and similar).
- Take into consideration polysemy of constructions that manipulate the argument-structure and/or valency, e.g. the reflexive marker (cp. the semantic map of reflexive markers in Haspelmath 2003, see Figure 1): anticausative—passive, reflexive—reciprocal (natural vs. canonical reciprocals; for the difference cf. Kemmer 1993 and Nedjalkov 2007):

Figure 1: Semantic map of basic reflexive and middle functions (on the basis of Haspelmath 2003: 225)

FIG. 8.9. A semantic map for reflexive and middle functions.

Natural reciprocals: the denoted situation is naturally conceived of as occurring mutually and simultaneously, e.g.

- (1) Pol. *A i B się objęli.*
 Lith. *A ir B ap-si-kabino.* = REFL (‘light marker’ in Kemmer’s 1993 terms)
 Russ. *A i B obnjali-s’.*
 ‘A and B embraced.’

Canonical reciprocals: the denoted situation is not naturally conceived of as occurring mutually and simultaneously, but becomes such one with REFL or a specialized marker, e.g.

- (2) Pol. *A i B pisali sobie listy.* = REFL
 Lith. *A ir B rašė vienas kitam laiškus.* (# *rašė-si*) = ‘one another’-
 Russ. *A i B pisali drug drugu pis’ma.* (# *pisali-s’*) quasi pronoun
 ‘A and B wrote each other letters.’ (# *themselves*)

(On the areal significance, especially of Lithuanian, cf. Wiemer 2019: §5.3.)

2.15. Types of secondary predicates: adjectives, adverbs, participles (including gerunds); distinction between resultative (*He pounded the metal flat*) vs. depictive (*He sat in the chair naked*) secondary predicates (cf. Schultze-Berndt & Himmelmann 2004). In distinction to modifiers of verbal action (see 2.8), we are here dealing with the modification of an argument of the main predicate.

2.16. Types of complex predicates or multi-verb constructions (with auxiliaries, phasal verbs, causative verbs).

- What are the morphosyntactic properties of such constructions as opposed to (i) one-word predicates and (ii) biclausal constructions?
- Do all types of complex predicates share basic morphosyntactic features or rather each kind of complex predicate has its own features? Consider such parameters as morphological categories available to the auxiliary/lexical verb (including agreement), word order freedom, partially independent/fully shared argument structure and/or adverbial modification, expression of coarguments (especially in coordination-based complex predicates), presence of overt connectives etc.
- What are the functions of such complex predicates (e.g. tense/aspect/modality, phasal meaning, causation, passivization), including language- or area-specific functions like that of the Russian “inexpectative” TAKE-construction, e.g. *vzjal i skazal* ‘(all of a sudden he) said’ (lit. ‘took and said’).

2.17. Patterns of predicative possession:

- HAVE vs. BE, marking of possessor and possessee.
- Possible relations (polysemy) with locative/existential predication.
- Range and intersection of subfunctions, if more than one pattern is used.
- Are there different coding techniques for inalienable vs. alienable possession?

2.18. Clause combining:

- What are the general patterns of clause combining in your language?
- Are there “balanced” constructions, i.e. involving verbal forms which can be used as independent predicates, and “deranked” constructions, i.e. those lacking some of the morphological or syntactic features of independent clauses (see questions regarding (non)finiteness above)?
- Are there coordinating conjunctions like AND or BUT?
- Are there complementizers like THAT or WHETHER?
- Are there subordinating conjunctions like IF, WHEN, ALTHOUGH, etc.?
- Are nonfinite or nominalized verbal forms productively employed for clausal complementation or adverbial subordination?
- What are the strategies of relative clause formation, especially in terms of balanced vs. deranked verbal forms? Are there relative pronouns (like Rus. *kotoryj*) or invariant relativizers (like Rus. *čto*)? Can the latter be also used as complementizers or adverbial subordinators (as e.g. Lith. dialectal *kur* ‘where; that’)? Can participles be used as heads of full-fledged relative clauses (e.g. containing arguments and adverbs), or only as one-word attributes? Which positions can be relativized by means of participles (see also 2.13)?
- What is (if any) the distribution of balanced (“finite”) vs. deranked (“nonfinite”) strategies of subordination — in terms of function/morphosyntax, register (written vs. spoken), style (official/“high” vs. colloquial/“low”) and token frequency?

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